

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSOCIATION OF GLIOBLASTOMA WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Glioblastoma is the most prevalent and aggressive primary brain tumor in adults, and its etiology and pathogenesis involve genetic susceptibility, environmental factors, and molecular alterations. Metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a cluster of conditions significantly associated with an increased risk of diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Emerging evidence suggests that metabolic dysregulation may be involved in the pathogenesis of glioblastoma, with chronic low-grade inflammation and insulin resistance creating a tumor-promoting environment. Studies indicate that patients with MetS may have a slightly higher prevalence of glioblastoma and worse overall survival. This article explores the complex relationship between glioblastoma and metabolic syndrome, highlighting potential therapeutic interventions and the need for further research.

Keywords: glioblastoma, metabolic syndrome, inflammation, insulin resistance, molecular alterations, insulin-like growth factor, overall survival, progression-free survival.

Introduction

Glioblastoma is the most prevalent and aggressive primary brain tumor in adults. It is characterized by necrosis and endothelial proliferation, and the World Health Organization (WHO) classifies it as a grade IV tumor [12, 18]. Secondary glioblastomas, which are a minority and correlate with younger age and more favorable outcomes, evolve from previously diagnosed WHO grade II or III gliomas and are associated with specific point mutations in isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH) genes [12, 18]. In contrast, the majority of glioblastomas are IDH wild-type, with typical molecular changes involving genes regulating receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK)/rat sarcoma (RAS)/phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K), p53, and retinoblastoma protein (RB) signaling [12, 18]. Standard treatment includes surgery, radiotherapy, and alkylating chemotherapy, with the promoter methylation of the MGMT gene predicting the benefit of temozolomide treatment [16, 17].

According to American Heart Association (AHA) [5], MetS is defined as the presence of at least three of the following criteria: elevated waist circumference (>102 cm in men and >88 cm in women); elevated triglycerides (>150 mg/dL); reduced high-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels (HDL-C) (<40 mg/dL in men and <50 mg/dL in woman); elevated blood pressure

(>130 mmHg systolic blood pressure or, >85 mmHg diastolic blood pressure); elevated fasting glucose (>100 mg/dL). MetS is significantly associated with an increased risk of diabetes and cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), which are the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide [2, 4]. The pathogenesis of MetS involves genetic and acquired factors leading to chronic low-grade inflammation and insulin resistance [2, 4].

Etiology and Pathogenesis of Glioblastoma

Gliomas, originating from astrocytic, oligodendroglia, and ependymal cells, account for over 70% of brain tumors, with glioblastoma being the most malignant type [12, 18]. The incidence rates of brain tumors have remained stable, with higher rates observed in developed countries [12, 18]. Genetic susceptibility and environmental factors, such as therapeutic X-irradiation, have been implicated in glioma risk, with children treated for acute lymphoblastic leukemia showing a significantly elevated risk of developing gliomas [12, 18].

The molecular pathogenesis of glioblastoma is complex and involves multiple genetic alterations. Key molecular changes in glioblastoma include alterations in the RTK/RAS/PI3K pathway, which is crucial for cell growth and survival [12]. Mutations in the p53 tu-

mor suppressor gene and disruptions in the RB signaling pathway also contribute to glioblastoma development [12, 18]. Furthermore, epigenetic modifications, such as MGMT promoter methylation, influence the tumor's response to alkylating agents like temozolomide. This highlights the importance of molecular profiling in guiding treatment strategies [12, 18].

Environmental factors also play a critical role in glioblastoma risk. Exposure to therapeutic X-irradiation, particularly in childhood, is a well-documented risk factor for gliomas and other brain tumors [12, 18]. Other potential environmental risk factors include occupational exposures and dietary factors, though these associations are less well established [12, 18]. Notably, N-nitroso compounds, which can be found in certain foods, have been linked to an increased risk of glioma, suggesting a possible dietary influence on glioblastoma development [12, 18].

Etiology and Pathogenesis of Metabolic Syndrome

The pathogenesis of MetS is primarily driven by insulin resistance, influenced by lifestyle factors like low physical activity and obesity, as well as genetic predisposition [2, 4]. Hormonal disturbances, particularly involving the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and increased cortisol levels, also play a role [2, 4]. These factors contribute to abdominal obesity, insulin resistance, hypertension, and dyslipidemia, leading to increased risks of type 2 diabetes and atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases [2, 4].

Insulin resistance, a hallmark of MetS, results in impaired glucose uptake and utilization, leading to hyperglycemia [2, 4]. This metabolic disturbance triggers a cascade of compensatory mechanisms, including increased insulin secretion by the pancreas [2, 4]. Over time, the persistent hyperinsulinemia state can exhaust pancreatic beta cells, leading to the development of type 2 diabetes [2, 4]. Concurrently, insulin resistance affects lipid metabolism, contributing to dyslipidemia characterized by elevated triglycerides and low HDL cholesterol levels [2, 4].

Central obesity, another key component of MetS, is strongly associated with increased visceral fat accumulation [2, 4]. Visceral fat is metabolically active and secretes various adipokines and pro-inflammatory cytokines that contribute to systemic inflammation and insulin resistance [2, 4]. This inflammatory state is further exacerbated by hormonal imbalances, particularly involving the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis [2, 4]. Increased cortisol levels, often resulting from chronic stress or other factors, promote abdominal fat deposition and further insulin resistance [2, 4].

Hypertension, another critical element of MetS, arises from complex interactions between insulin resistance, obesity, and endothelial dysfunction [2, 4]. Insulin resistance impairs nitric oxide-mediated vasodilation, leading to increased vascular resistance and hypertension [2, 4]. Additionally, obesity contributes to increased blood volume and cardiac output, further elevating blood pressure [2, 4].

Association Between Glioblastoma and Metabolic Syndrome

In addition to increasing cardiovascular burden, MetS is mentioned in the literature as a risk factor for several types of cancer (liver, colon, bladder, pancreatic, breast, and endometrial) [3]. Each component of MetS is also assumed to be responsible for increased mortality in cancer patients [14]. Their additive and synergistic interplay may comprise to the overall mechanisms by which MetS can affect the risk of cancer development and progression. Insulin resistance and inflammation are the main mechanisms of these associations [3, 14].

Emerging evidence suggests that metabolic dysregulation may be involved in the pathogenesis of glioblastoma. Chronic low-grade inflammation, a hallmark of MetS, may create a tumor-promoting environment for glioblastoma [7, 11, 13, 18]. Pro-inflammatory cytokines and adipokines secreted by visceral fat can induce oxidative stress and DNA damage, potentially contributing to glioblastoma development [7, 11, 13]. Studies of glioblastoma demonstrate that the insulin-like growth factor (IGF) system plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of this tumor. Hyperinsulinemia is associated with tumor progression through activation of the IGF receptor cascade. The IGF system activates mitogenic and survival mediators, promoting an increase in the number of glioblastoma growth cells, cell proliferation and migration [13].

Metabolic syndrome is also associated with alterations in cellular metabolism, which may impact glioblastoma biology. For instance, dysregulated glucose and lipid metabolism in MetS could provide a favorable metabolic environment for glioblastoma cells, which rely heavily on glycolysis and lipid synthesis for energy production and growth [7, 11, 13, 18].

Proving the importance of altered tumor metabolism as one of key hallmarks of glioblastoma, enhanced by MetS, Khan et al. conducted a study, in which they inhibited glioblastoma cell glycolysis with the use of stiripentol, a lactate dehydrogenase inhibitor. This impaired infiltration of glioblastoma by macrophages and consequently its cells' glycolysis, proliferation and survival [8].

Another pathway of association between MetS and glioblastoma, according to Herr et al., is through autotaxin (ATX), a soluble extracellular enzyme that is abundant in mammalian plasma and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). It has two known enzymatic activities, acting as both a phosphodiesterase and a phospholipase. The majority of its biological effects have been associated with its ability to liberate lysophosphatidic acid (LPA) from its substrate, lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC). LPA has diverse pleiotropic effects in the central nervous system (CNS) and other tissues via the activation of a family of six cognate G protein-coupled receptors. These LPA receptors (LPARs) are expressed in some combination in all known cell types in the CNS where they mediate such fundamental cellular processes as proliferation, differentiation, migration, chronic inflammation, and cytoskeletal organization. As a result, dysregulation of LPA content may contribute to many CNS and PNS disorders such as glioblastoma and metabolic syndrome-induced brain damage [6].

In glioblastoma cells, cholesterol metabolism was also found to be impaired in terms of increased absorption of cholesterol by this tumour. Although the study by Cermenati et al. did not consider this in terms of the presence of MetS, it is well known about lipid metabolism disruptions in the presence of this syndrome [1].

Pyruvate carboxylase (PC), an anaplerotic enzyme, plays an essential role in various cellular metabolic pathways including gluconeogenesis, de novo fatty acid synthesis, amino acid synthesis, and glucose-induced insulin secretion. Disregulation of PC expression or activity has long been known to be associated with metabolic syndrome. More recent studies also show that PC is strongly involved in tumorigenesis in several cancers, including glioblastoma [9].

Studies indicate that patients with MetS may have a slightly higher prevalence of glioblastoma compared to the general population, with worse overall survival observed among glioblastoma patients with MetS [7, 11, 13].

A retrospective cohort study revealed that hypertension, hyperglycemia, and dyslipidemia were negatively associated with survival in glioblastoma patients, while BMI was not [10, 13]. Additionally, the accumulation of metabolic risk factors correlated with decreased overall survival [13]. Some studies even suggest that obesity may, in part, be responsible for improving the prognosis of these patients. In the literature, the prognostic advantage of obese people is referred to as the "obesity paradox". Inadequate measure of adiposity by using BMI, nutritional reserves that help patients resist radiochemotherapy treatments, less aggressive forms of cancer, and stronger immune and inflammatory responses are possible explanations for this phenomenon [10]. In a study of impacts of each component of MetS in overall survival (OS) and progression-free survival (PFS) of glioblastoma patients, obese people had a median of 11.6 months before progression compared with 7.5 months in non-obese patients (log-rank $p=0.032$) [10]. In another retrospective study of the impact of BMI on OS and PFS of surgically resected primary glioblastoma patients, median OS was 21.3 months in obese patients vs 16.2 months in the non-obese ($p = 0.017$) and 16 months in the normal weight ($p = 0.007$). Median PFS in obese individuals was 9 months in comparison to 6 months in the normal-weight subgroup ($p = 0.04$) and 7 months in the non-obese ($p = 0.050$) [15].

Epidemiological studies have shown that the prevalence of MetS in glioblastoma patients varies, with some studies reporting a higher prevalence compared to the general population, while others report a lower prevalence [7, 11, 13]. Rogers et al. demonstrate that patients with MetS and glioblastoma who had received a full schedule of radiation and temozolomide had a median OS of 12.4 months, compared with 17.9 months in patients without MetS (p -value 0.18) [13]. McManus et al. also found a reduced OS in patients with MetS, irrespective of treatment (8 vs. 13 months, $p=0.16$) [11]. Lucas et al. did not find a statistically significant difference in OS of patients with MetS and glioblastoma, and there was a trend toward increased survival of patients with this syndrome (19.7 vs. 17.7 months for

OS, log-rank $p=0.085$). They also did not find an association between MetS and PFS (9.9 vs. 7.9 months for PFS log-rank $p=0.076$) [10]. However, they had some limitations of the study that may have contributed to contradictory results in terms of the prevalence and survival of glioblastoma patients.

Despite all of those variations, the consistent finding across the majority of studies is that MetS is associated with worse survival outcomes in glioblastoma patients, highlighting the need for further research for deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms and potential therapeutic interventions [7, 11, 13].

Conclusion

The association between glioblastoma and metabolic syndrome is multifaceted, with chronic low-grade inflammation and insulin resistance playing crucial roles. The presence of MetS may contribute to a higher prevalence of glioblastoma and worse survival outcomes in patients. While some studies suggest a potential "obesity paradox" in glioblastoma patients, the majority of evidence points to a negative impact of MetS on glioblastoma prognosis. Further research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and develop potential therapeutic interventions targeting metabolic dysregulation in glioblastoma. Addressing MetS in patients with glioblastoma may offer a novel approach to improving treatment outcomes and overall survival.

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